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New Roles of a Librarian: The Experience of Grinchenko University

Objective. The article considers the transformation of the roles of librarians in the modern information society: from information providers to educators, which is a sign of the successful process of internationalization of higher education. The object of the research is the new forms of work of librarians on the example of the experience of Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University and the First Summer School for Beginners and Experienced Scientists “Scientific Career at the International Level: Tools for Researchers and the English Language” held in June 2024. **Methods.** The methods of marketing and monitoring research are described to determine the most popular topics and emotionally attractive names among the target audience. **Results.** The results and their discussion focus on the fact that the experience of the Grinchenko University Summer School showed the possibility of high-quality training and advanced training of scientists of different levels and fields of knowledge on the basis of the library of the higher education institution. **Conclusions.** The change in the role of librarians from information providers to educators in the context of internationalization of higher education is inevitable. Moreover, librarians are forced to be one step ahead of the rest of the university's scientists.

Keywords: changing roles of librarians; summer school for researchers; advanced training; library; internationalization of higher education

Introduction

In today's information society, the role of librarians is undergoing significant transformations. From traditional information providers, they are gradually turning into educators and mentors who help researchers navigate the complex world of modern science. Over the past decades, scientists of Ukraine and the world have been actively talking about the development of new services in the work of libraries in order to meet the requirements of modernity (Kari & Oyeniran, 2019), (Polishchuk, & Shevchuk, 2022).

This article is devoted to the analysis of new roles of librarians based on the experience of Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University in the context of internationalization of higher education.

In June 2024, the First Summer School for Beginners and Experienced Scientists “Scientific Career at the International Level: Tools for Researchers and the English Language” was held at Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University, which was attended by young and experienced scientists from different parts of Ukraine. Among the participants are postgraduate students and experienced scientists from Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University and representatives of the National Aerospace University named after M. Ye. Zhukovsky “Kharkiv Aviation Institute”, H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Odesa State University of Internal Affairs, State Biotechnical University, Dragomanov Ukrainian State University, Municipal extracurricular school “Kyiv Youth Academy of Sciences”, and other institutions of Ukraine.

The aim of the advanced training program was to develop skills in the use of research tools in the preparation of academic publications for the successful international scientific career. The trainers were employees of the University Library: Director Tetiana Opryshko, Researcher Serhii Nazarovets, Junior Researcher Halyna Tymofieieieva, Head of the Department Anastasiia Lytvynova, as well as Dean of the Faculty of Romano-Germanic Philology of Grinchenko University Valentyn Yakuba.

CHANGING ROLES: FROM INFORMATION PROVIDERS TO EDUCATORS

As a result of successful completion of the course, the participants received certificates of advanced training in the amount of 60 hours.

A marketing and monitoring study was conducted beforehand and the most demanded topics were identified. The Summer School program includes the following:

- Search for literature and sources of scientific information.
- Scientific cooperation and co-authorship.
- Presentation of research results.
- Bibliometry and scientometrics.
- Open science.
- English for researchers.

The Summer School was held online.

Most of the classes were conducted by the library staff, and the Dean of the University's Faculty of Romano-Germanic Philology was invited to teach English classes.

The participants of the Summer School were representatives of various industries and disciplines, educational and scientific institutions who were interested in scientific issues and who sought to:

- develop skills in working with databases of scientific citations, preparation for publication in international journals of their own scientific works;
- protect their copyrights;
- promote their scientific works and establish international scientific contacts;
- to deepen their understanding of scientometrics, sources of scientometric information, scientometric analysis and indicators of scientific influence.

The School had three components:

1. Lectures (online, Ukrainian).
2. Practice. Each participant received practical tasks, which they worked out independently and checked in the mode of individual online consultations with trainers.
3. Project. The participants chose a scientific journal, with the help of a trainer adapted their scientific works to the requirements of the journal and sent them for publication.

The program of the advanced training course was clearly structured and logically constructed. Participants noted this in their feedback after the training. An important stage was to start classes with the concept of the scientific method and the importance of scientific research, choosing a research topic, formulating hypotheses and research tasks, creating a research plan and schedule, using academic databases and search strategies, critically evaluating scientific literature, and working with bibliographic managers. Special attention was also paid to English classes for researchers. It considered the structure of the scientific text: writing an abstract – theses – articles, defining logical markers, set phrases, textual links, translating the terminology of one's field: searching for English-language correspondences and forming one's own word forms. As a result of the comprehensive preparation of the program and the well-coordinated work of the trainers, the participants of the summer school received the most important thing – the desire and readiness for scientific achievements.

The event received positive feedback from the participants and confirmed its relevance and necessity.

Methods

Prior to the announcement of the recruitment for the Grinchenko University Summer School, a marketing and monitoring study was conducted for researchers to identify the most popular topics and an emotionally appealing title. The target audience was the participants of advanced training programs for scientific-pedagogical and scientific workers of Grinchenko University, PhD students of the University.

Marketing and monitoring research using Google form tools (Potrashkova, Raiko, Tseitlin, Savchenko, & Szabolcs, 2018) was identified by us as the best method of collecting the necessary information due to its efficiency. The unconditional advantages of this method are also convenience for respondents, the ability to monitor the progress of the study in real time, a certain format and the ability to obtain quick statistics and data visualization. With its help, we chose a version of the name of the Summer School and identified the topics that are most interesting and relevant to potential participants.

In addition, the very preparation of the questionnaire forces the author of the questions to substantiate the problem situation more thoughtfully, to clearly identify the object and subject, purpose, and basic hypotheses of the research. When creating an online Google Forms questionnaire, it is imperative to take into account the type of information that will be processed, so you need to choose the right reference scale, on the basis of which the survey results should be calculated.

In our survey regarding the choice of the most eloquent and attractive name of the Summer School, we applied an interval metric scale, which in Google Forms is implemented through questions of the “with answer options” type.

We offered the respondents 10 formulations of the name of the Summer School, from which they had to choose one. The survey involved 75 respondents from among PhD students and persons with a scientific degree. Since the potential target audience of the Summer School is young scientists and those who already have experience in defending a thesis and in scientific publications in various journals, we consider the sample of survey participants to be relevant in terms of quality.

Results and Discussion

On the way to the development of the scientific component of the academic library, one of the main areas of work is to support scientific research (Singh & Siwach, 2024). Given the challenges faced by modern Ukrainian scientists, librarians are gradually becoming lecturers and mentors on digital tools for researchers, the search for literature and sources of scientific information, maintaining author profiles, scientometrics, academic integrity and much more (Opryshko & Skladannyi, 2020).

The implementation of the principles of open science is relevant for Ukrainian scientists (Nazarovets, 2022), but not everyone knows about the available practices. Therefore, librarians take on an educational function on these and many other issues.

The experience of the library of Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University is based on the research of the demand for the most popular topics from Ukrainian researchers and timely response to their challenges. In the era of prosperity of factories of scientific publications and the unmotivated use of artificial intelligence, the issue of high-quality scientific research remains relevant.

The First Summer School for Beginners and Experienced Scientists “Scientific Career at the International Level: Tools for Researchers and the English Language” held at the Grinchenko

University confirmed the relevance of high-quality training and advanced training on the basis of the library of the higher education institution.

Conclusions

Changing the roles of librarians from information providers to educators in the context of internationalization of higher education is inevitable in today's information society. Librarians must adapt to the new challenges and needs of the scientific community. One of the main areas of librarians' work is to support scientific research. This includes training researchers in the use of digital tools, literature retrieval, author profiling, scientometrics, and academic integrity. The implementation of the principles of open science is relevant for Ukrainian scientists. Librarians take on an educational function on these issues, helping researchers navigate new practices. The experience of the library of Borys Grinchenko Kyiv Metropolitan University demonstrates the importance of researching the demand for the most popular topics among researchers and responding to their challenges in a timely manner. Qualitative training and advanced training: The Summer School for Beginners and Experienced Scientists "Scientific Career at the International Level: Tools for Researchers and the English Language" showed the possibility of carrying out qualitative training and advanced training on the basis of the library of a higher education institution. The event received positive feedback from the participants, which confirms its relevance and necessity. This indicates the success of new approaches in the work of librarians. Librarians are forced to be one step ahead of the rest of the university's scientists, constantly developing and improving their knowledge and skills to effectively support scientific activities. These findings highlight the importance of the new roles of librarians in the modern scientific environment and their key role in supporting and developing scientific research.

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Нові ролі бібліотекарів: досвід Університету Грінченка

Мета. У статті розглядається трансформація ролей бібліотекарів у сучасному інформаційному суспільстві: від постачальників інформації до педагогів, що є ознакою успішного процесу інтернаціоналізації вищої освіти. Об'єктом дослідження стали нові форми роботи бібліотекарів на прикладі досвіду Київського столичного університету імені Бориса Грінченка та проведення в червні 2024 року літньої школи для початківців та досвідчених учених «Наукова кар'єра на міжнародному рівні: інструменти для дослідників та англійська мова». **Методика.** Описано методи маркетингово-моніторингового дослідження для визначення найбільш затребуваних тем та емоційно привабливої назви серед цільової аудиторії. **Результати.** В результатах та їх обговоренні акцентовано увагу на тому, що досвід проведення літньої школи Університету Грінченка засвідчив можливість здійснення якісної підготовки та підвищення кваліфікації науковців різних рівнів та галузей знань на базі бібліотеки закладу вищої освіти. **Висновки.** Висновки про те, що зміна ролей бібліотекарів від постачальників інформації до педагогів в умовах інтернаціоналізації вищої освіти є неминучою. Ба більше, бібліотекарі змушені бути на крок попереду від решти науковців університету.

Ключові слова: зміна ролей бібліотекарів; літня школа для дослідників; підвищення кваліфікації; бібліотека; інтернаціоналізація вищої освіти

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